

Some important traditional medicinal plants used to cure child health illnesses

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ABSTRACT

India has an abundant source of medicinal herbs. Plant-based medications have been used for traditional healthcare since prehistoric times due to its ease of use and cost-effectiveness. Based on traditional healers or practitioners who use their invaluable knowledge to treat plant-based traditional treatments for child health care. The information gathered from traditional practices was also cross-checked to ensure its legitimacy. Traditional healers typically utilize leaves, flowers, fruits, seeds, and bark in the form of a decoction, paste, extract, juice, ash, or infusion to treat a variety of diseases. The current study found that plant-based traditional information was collected and documented from many traditional healers of the Parali tahasil using questionnaires and personal interviews. The practitioners use common therapeutic plant materials such as Gulvel, Aghada, and Halad. The most popular plants utilized by practitioners are herbs, followed by shrubs, trees, and climbers. This study found that documenting ethnobotanical knowledge in the administration of local health care is the first step toward opening new doors for researchers in the field of child health care.

Keywords: Researchers, Child health care, Medicinal herbs.

INTRODUCTION

Information about medicinal plants in India has been acquired over many centuries based on numerous archaic restorative systems, such as ayurveda, unani, and siddha (Lone and Bhardwaj, 2013). According to the World Health Organization, traditional medicine serves over 80% of the world's population, either directly or indirectly (Rath *et al.*, 2009; Pattnaik *et al.*, 2006). India is one of the world's most biodiverse regions, with diverse ethnic, linguistic, socioeconomic, and cultural zones. Thus, it is reasonable to anticipate this country to have firsthand knowledge of therapeutic herbs and their usage in the treatment of a wide range of illnesses. In rural India, 70% of inhabitants rely on conventional medicine (Rao and Laxmi, 2012). The annual global market for herbal medicines reached more than \$60 billion in 2000, and it is continuously increasing at a pace of 15 to 25 percent (WHO, 2008). In India, healthcare prices have risen considerably during the previous decade. According to a Towers Watson research (based on data from top global insurance companies), India witnessed 22% increase in

health care expenses in 2006. It reaches 12% in 2009 and is anticipated to rise again to 13% in 2012. People are looking for easy and cost-effective medicines to improve their quality of life (Biswas, 2012). The steep rise in health-care costs, combined with the threat of increasing side-effect risks from synthetic medicine, is convincing the public to believe in low-cost alternative medicines with few or no side effects, such as Ayurveda, Homoeopathy, Siddha, Unani, Yoga, Naturopathy, and others which provide a wide range of preventive and remedial treatments that are both cost-effective and efficient.

Parli Vaijnath is a city and municipal council in Beed district, Maharashtra. It serves as the administrative center for the Parli taluka in Beed district. It is one of 11 Talukas in Bid district. Parli Taluka consists of 105 villages and one town. As per the Census India 2011, Parli Taluka has 57806 homes, population of 287208 of which 149421 are males and 137787 are females. Children aged 0 to 6 account for 39846 of the total population, or 13.87%. Prior to independence, it was a part of the former Hyderabad state. It was included in the State of Maharashtra in 1960. Topographically, the parali taluka divided into two deferent region e.g. Godavari valley and Balaghat range. In now day's majority of this region's land has been turned to agricultural use. Environmental degradation, deforestation, and agricultural development are all contributing to the decline of traditional knowledge. Therefore, acquiring information about therapeutic plants is an essential need. Thus, the goal of this research was to interact with local traditional healers and document their knowledge of medicinal plants, their practice, and the treatment of various maladies.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

3.1 Ethno Botanical Survey:

The practice of plant based medicinal system is widespread among the ethnic people of Parali Taluka, and it is intensely rooted in their socioeconomic traditions. Though, the documentation of local medicinal practices is conspicuously missing for the region. Considering the immense cultural and ethno-linguistic diversity of the tribal people of the taluka, several field interviews in the form of semi-structured questionnaire were designed to cover as in Parli municipal as possible, in order to take full advantage of the diversity of knowledge and the plant species

used in conventional therapy. Collected information is useful to curing several ailments on child health care by using different medicinal plants. Take several visits for ethnic places in different seasons when plants get flowering. Informants getting the information about local names, used plant parts, formulation and dosages were also documented. The aims of this investigation were systematically clarified to all the informants before the interview (Cunningham, 2001).

3.2 Collection and Identification of Medicinal Plant:

Fresh and healthy plant materials of medicinal herbs were collected in the month of August- 2020 to November- 2020 from different location of Parli taluka of Beed district. Identification of plant species were confirmed using Flora of Marathwada by Naik *et al.*, 1998. Collected plant materials were pressed, dried, and mounted on herbarium sheet for further study.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Most of preparation was arranged from fresh and healthy plant material in the form of a decoction, powder and paste. Nearly all used approach of medication administration is oral ingestion, followed by external use. A large amount of diseases and pains were usually treated either with a single plant or a mixture of plant parts. In some cases, ointments like mustered oil, ghee (a remedy from milk) etc. and other ingredients such as black peeper, ginger, tulsi, etc. were also used to make ethnic formulations along with the parts of plant species. In children diseases the highest use report in the present study were documented for *Ocimum sanctum*, *Azardicta indica*, *Terminalia bellirica*, *Terminalia chebula*, *Phyllanthus emblica*, *Adhatoda vasica*, *Acacia nilotica* etc. Present study aims was undertaken to explore the plant based traditional remedies, and local health care practioner from Parali taluka of Maharashtra state. For this purpose series of field surveys were carried out. The information on traditional medicinal plants was collected through conversations, questionnaires etc. with local traditional healers (Baidyas, Ojhas, Traditional healer, aged knowledgeable persons). The information collected from the informants along with the medicinal plants, their local names, plant parts used as a medicine, formulation and doses has been given in Table 1. Traditional medicines are easily available and safe to cure various health problems. In recent era almost every nation of the world used it.

Table 1: Plant based herbal remedies practiced for child health

Sr. No.	Remedies	Disease treated	Name of healer
1.	Some small pieces of stem of Gulvel boiled with one glass of water up to remaining half glass then filter it and used an empty stomach at early morning.	Fever (Hadi tap)	Mr. Govind Manik Solanke
2.	Drink ½ cup of leaf juice of <i>Achyranthes aspera</i> (Aghada) in early morning with empty stomach.	To increase Appetite	Ms. Rukmini Dharmraj Tambud
3.	Burn the leaves of <i>Ficus religiosa</i> ash and few powder of urmeric is mixed with water take orally.	Vomiting	Mr. Kulkarni Mama Bhisegaokar
4.	Take bitter gourd juice, turmeric and pinch of salt mix it well and lick with honey.	Stomach ache	Ms. Anu Balaji Chaure
5.	Take a decoction of Leaf juice of <i>Tinospora cardifolia</i> twice a day for 3 days.	Fever	Mr. Sopan Limbaji Mundhe
6.	4-5 Fruits of <i>Ficus carica</i> (anjir) given twice a day.	Cough, Constipation	Mr. Vitthal Dharmraj Tambud
7.	1 cup of <i>Melia azedarach</i> decoction is used orally before breakfast.	Diabetes	Mr. Vitthal Dharmraj Tambud
8.	5-6 Seed of <i>Embelia ribes</i> boiled with 1 cup of water up to 1/3 and drink it after cooled down for 7 days.	Remove worm, constipation	Mr. Ramesh Balasaheb Shinde
9.	Boiled 8-10 curry leaves in water then add trifala powder and amla powder in 1:1 ratio mix well take it at bed time for 7 weeks.	Early greying hair, Hairfall	Mr. Ankush Bhimrao Mundhe
10.	Take some turmeric powder with jiggery powder boil it with some water and drink before bed.	Cold, Dry cough	Mr. Abhay Vithal Lonikar
11.	Take 1 glass of water and add it 2 spoon of sugar and pinch of salt mixed well and give it for several intervals.	Loose motion	Mr. Hanumant Namdev Nagargoje
12.	Take roasted white sesame seeds, black sesame seeds and flax seeds grind them with the help of grinder then add it jaggery powder and make ladoos give it early morning.	Calcium Deficiency	Ms. Mandakini Jarichand Mundhe

Hence it is a best choice for alternative medicine due to its huge demand (Aziz *et al.*, 2018). In several formulations, number of part was used. Such as Leaves, rhizomes, roots, and the whole plant, it is most important hazards in the restoration of the medicinal plants (Ahmad *et al.*, 2009).

CONCLUSION

In this study revealed that how different interviewing procedures facilitate to gather the information concerning the name of the diseases treated plants and their usage, with their mode of direction. Total of 12 types of local ailments was treated with 12 phyto-therapeutic uses in this district. The manufacturing process of herbal preparation is yet a secret and passed on generation after generation vocally.

Appropriate examination of herbal formulations and phyto-constituents of used plants can open new entrance for the researchers. However, ethno-botanical facts is the basis of further justification of practices and plant uses in the context of a professional approach to develop new herbal drug (Muhammad *et al.*, 2005).

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no competing interests.

Data Availability Statement: Not applicable.

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